

The Space Station Information System
and Software Support Environment

Clarence W. Pittman

Director, Software Technology Division
NASA Space Station Program Office

The Space Station will be a large, permanent, multi-purpose facility with comfortable living quarters for a crew of up to eight people. It will consist of four habitable modules and a truss to which payloads which do not require human involvement can be attached. It is intended to accommodate a wide variety of science and technology projects (astronomical and geophysical observations, materials and life sciences, etc.) and, as it evolves, to serve as an assembly, servicing, and departure point for other space missions. The truss, utility services, and two of the modules will be provided by NASA, one module will be provided by the National Space Development Agency of Japan, and the other by the European Space Agency. The entire manned base will be carried into orbit and assembled in nineteen increments over a period of two years around 1995.

A large part of the value of the Space Station will reside in the information exchanged between it and the related ground facilities. To insure that this exchange is effective, the Space Station Information System (SSIS) has been identified as an explicit element of the program and a management structure has been put in place to oversee the development of the end-to-end system, including those elements not provided by NASA. This will involve identifying all the components of the SSIS and the people responsible for each, comparing their schedules, establishing interface and protocol agreements, and providing for testing the overall system. The SSIS management intention is that the non-NASA participants, including the international partners, will have complete freedom in the design of

their hardware and software, providing that they satisfy the agreed upon interfaces.

The SSIS is an extensive collection of hardware (computers, networks, facilities) and software, whose primary purpose is to carry data between a space-based source and a ground-based user. The data source could be a scientific instrument on the manned base or on a platform; it could be a piece of on-board equipment; or even a crew member. The ground-based user could be an experimenter operating from his home institution or an operator based in a spacecraft control facility. The data itself might be scientific data; housekeeping data used to monitor equipment health and safety; a database query; or audio and video data forming part of a space-ground teleconference. While the situation is not completely symmetrical, most of these data-flows will also occur, simultaneously, from ground to space.

The collection of hardware elements involved in this process is large and varied, consisting of more than ninety space and ground elements which combine to form the SSIS. Some of these elements are new and unique to the SSP while others (such as the Tracking Data Relay Satellite System (TDRSS)) are extended versions of existing NASA institutional capabilities. Some elements are outside of SSP (and even NASA) control, such as customer facilities and public communications networks. However, being connected to the SSIS and using its services, they can be considered as SSIS elements.

In the past, space mission data systems tended to be rather inflexible, schedule-driven systems which were labor-intensive to operate. Typically, users' data would be delivered several days (or longer) after reception, frequently in formats unique to NASA. The SSIS concept involves some significant improvements:

- . The trend is away from schedule-driven and towards data-driven systems - within certain prearranged limits, the system will autonomously accommodate changes in data rates and data destinations. This results in operations which are more flexible, less labor-intensive, and give better service to users.

- . A necessary building block in the construction of data-driven systems is the autonomous data unit - instead of appearing to the data system as anonymous bit streams, basic data units will be packetized and self-identifying. This allows many of the data system functions, such as routing data to users and removing data transport artifacts, to be entirely automated and generic in nature.

- . Packetized data can be further packed into 'virtual channels' so that many logically distinct data streams can be multiplexed into the same physical medium (for example, the space-ground link via TDRS).

- . In addition to the program benefits of these techniques, the adoption of packetized, data-driven methods has equal benefit to the user community in terms of increased operational flexibility and reduced software development effort.

Another way in which the SSIS differs from previous data systems is in the concepts of tele-operations and tele-analysis. The tele-operations concept is often described as the ability for a customer to interact with his payload as if that payload were in a laboratory 'next door'. The realization of

this concept imposes some stringent requirements on the intervening data systems:

- . They must provide constant, standard interfaces so that the payload/user interface looks the same regardless of whether the payload is on a testbench in the manufacturer's facility, in an integration facility at the launch site, or in orbit attached to the station or a platform.

- . They must provide data transparency - transporting data with minimum interference, regardless of the data content.

- . They must transport data with minimum delay so that the investigator can interactively change the course of an observation based on current information.

- . They must provide all of the above regardless of the customer's physical location: at his home institution, at a NASA facility, or at an international location.

Tele-analysis extends the concept to the ground processing of payload (and other) data. It includes the ability to locate useful data in distributed databases and archives, to extract and receive sub-sets regardless of the physical location of the data, and finally, to combine and reprocess datasets (possibly from different investigations) to produce new datasets of increased utility.

Similarly, the software for the SSIS will be large and complex, developed by many groups of people at many locations, and expected to operate safely and undergo extensive evolution over the life of the Space Station. The Software Support Environment (SSE) is being developed to control the development and maintenance of the SSIS software. Its purpose is to minimize the cost of the software over its life cycle while ensuring a high degree of safety and reliability. It embodies the "tools and rules"

i.e., the computer programs, procedures, and standards for the management, development, configuration control, integration, test and verification, and maintenance of the SSIS software. Virtually all software developed for the Space Station will use the SSE.

The SSE will reside in numerous facilities: the Software Support Environment Development Facility (SSEDF); a number of Software Production Facilities (SPF's); and the Multi System Integration Facility (MSIF). As its name implies, the SSEDF, located in Houston, is where the SSE will be developed. The SPF's will be at the locations where SSIS software is being produced. A tailored subset of the total SSE will be assembled at the SSEDF and installed at each SPF. The MSIF is the location at which the software elements produced and tested at the SPF's will be integrated and tested. It will contain sufficient simulations/emulations and/or prototypes of the Space Station Systems to allow the software to be tested in a realistic environment.

The SSE will control all phases of the software process, from development project initiation to operation and maintenance. When a software development project is initiated, the Project Manager will interact with the SSE to identify the project, the organization which will execute it, and the lines of authority within the organization. The SSE will subsequently report status and problems appropriately. He will also identify the tasks within the project and the personnel assigned to the tasks and the SSE will then control the access and activities of the personnel, i.e., testers can not alter code, designers can not perform formal verification testing, etc. The SSE will not permit the project to proceed until these task/personnel relationships are defined. Also during the project initiation, the SSE will assist the project manager to tailor the software life cycle model to fit the particular project and provide him with templates of the required documentation.

The SSE provides an extensive set of tools for the design, development, and integration of the software. For design and development, these include tools for requirements and traceability analyses, preliminary design, detailed design, coding and documentation standards compliance, code analysis, interactive de-bugging, etc. For test and verification, the SSE will have tools to evaluate requirements and design adherence, verify test completeness and comprehensiveness, configure the system for the test, perform the test and record the results, and identify and record deficiencies. Throughout the process, the SSE will use a DBMS to store and retrieve all the data objects produced by the project and it will support configuration management by retaining the currently approved versions of all controlled products.

The SSE software can be thought of as a collection of functional elements distributed in an architectural framework. The functional elements are: process management; software management support; software production; modeling, simulation, and software checkout; integration, test, and verification; data reconfiguration; and training. These functional elements are distributed among four architectural elements, which are called the Framework; Tools; Host System Software; and SSE Management. The Framework provides the functionality and control of the SSE. Users access the life-cycle products, tools, tests, and data through the Framework. The Tools element provides what its name implies. The Host System Software contains functions typical of host operating systems and utilities. These include executive, data base management, host configuration control, and communications. The SSE management element provides non-development management functions such as incorporation of non-SSE inputs, system performance monitoring, system management and resource analyses.

In addition, the SSE software includes a Human/Computer Interface; a Test and Tools Harness, which provides the interface between the Framework and the Tools; and a Distributed Ada Interface Set, a standard layer of interface services that bridges between the logical and physical views of the system.

Physically, each SPF will consist of one or more host computers, a collection of work stations, a local area network, and access to wide area networks. It will be designed to be hardware-independent and to accommodate technology upgrades transparently. Initially, the host computers will be from the VAX 8000 series and the IBM 3090 series, and the work stations will be Apple Macintosh II, IBM PC/AT compatible, and Apollo Series 3000. The local network will be an Ethernet-based TCP/IP LAN. In addition, there will be a specially designed Simulation Interface Buffer to provide an interface between the SPF and local simulations/emulations/prototypes of other Space Station systems.